

EOOSC-IF

Guidelines for Onboarding Resources to EOOSC Exchange (v5.0)

Version 5.0
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EOSC-IF / EOSC Profiles: **Guidelines for Onboarding Resources to EOSC** **Exchange (v5.0)**

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Public

Abstract

This EOSC Interoperability Guideline (IG) describes EOSC Profiles (V5.0), which are metadata schemas for the description of services, research products or other research artefacts that their providers choose to share with the EOSC user community through the EOSC Exchange, as well as for describing the organisations offering to provide these resources to EOSC. Any provider or other responsible party (the "Provider" or the "Catalogue Operator") that intends to include one or more research resources ("Resources") in EOSC must use the appropriate EOSC Profile to describe both themselves and those resources in the machine-readable digital formats described in this IG. Once described, the Provider or Catalogue Operator submits EOSC Profile records for processing as described in this IG, including review of its compliance with the Rules of Participation and Inclusion Criteria. If the processing is successful, the subject of each approved EOSC Profile will be listed, findable and accessible in the EOSC Marketplace and can be integrated with other EOSC Core Services, pursuant to the respective EOSC IGs for those services.

Version History

Version	Date	Authors/Contributors	Description
V5.0a	20/10/2023	Mark Dietrich (EGI Foundation)	Partial draft
V5.0b	13/11/2023	Mark Dietrich, Diego Scardaci (EGI), Luciano Gaido (INFN), Mark van de Sanden (SURF), Michelle Williams (Geant), Anke Friedrich (Geant), Raimundas Tuminauskus (PSNC)	Complete Initial Draft
V5.0c	6/12/20023	Mark Dietrich (EGI), Paul Millar (DESY), Kostas Koumantaros (GRNET), Mark van de Sanden (SURF), Thanassis Mantes (ARC)	Finalize version numbering policy, onboarding diagrams, counts of entity types
V5.0d	30/1/2024	Daan Broeder (CLARIN), Sally Chambers (DARIAH)	Final review by Technical Coordination Board
V5.0 final	6/2/2024	Mark Dietrich (EGI Foundation)	Final Version submitted to EC

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Glossary

Term	Definition
AAI (Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure)	A service (or distributed set of services) which enables users to be identified and to access protected information, other services or functionality.
API	Application Programming Interface
Community Catalogue Operator	An organisation operating an EOSC-compliant community catalogue and responsible for the onboarding and validating selected resources from that community catalogue into the EOSC Exchange.
Catalogue Operator Representative (COR)	An individual representing the Community Catalogue who is mandated to record information about the catalogue and for onboarding and maintaining the catalogue in the EOSC Exchange.

Community Catalogue	A catalogue of resources from a particular community. To be eligible for onboarding into the EOSC Exchange, such a catalogue needs to comply with the EOSC-Exchange Community Catalogue inclusion criteria. It may then be onboarded by a Catalogue Operator Representative on behalf of the Community Catalogue Operator. Unlike Data Sources, Community Catalogues can also contain resources such as Services and Training Resources, as well as Data Sources
Data Source	A service that links to collections of research products (see Research Product) as well as services that provide data in response to queries. Unlike Community Catalogues, Data Sources do not refer to services.
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud. An envisioned federation of research (data) infrastructures that will create a web of FAIR data and services for science. EOSC will be a key enabler for Open Science and will support researchers in sharing and exploiting research products (e.g as data, publications, and code) through value-added horizontal (i.e. cross-disciplinary) and thematic (i.e. discipline-specific) services. EOSC was developed in an initial implementation phase from 2016-2020 under Horizon 2020 and will be expanded in a second implementation phase via the EOSC Partnership from 2021-2027 under Horizon Europe.
EOSC Association	An international non-profit organisation (AISBL) based in Brussels to represent the interest of the EOSC stakeholder community. The association is a partner with the European Commission in the EOSC Partnership and has developed and will continuously update a Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) to advise the European Commission on the development and implementation of EOSC.
EOSC Interoperability Advisory Board (EIAB)	Responsible for overseeing the EOSC Interoperability Framework; endorses/deprecates guidelines based on the recommendations of the EIAC. A temporary project-based composition has been established during the EOSC Future project, consisting of the Technical Coordination Board.
EOSC Interoperability Area Chairs (EIAC)	Responsible for performing the initial assessment of the proposed guidelines; makes recommendations to the EIAB as regards candidates for inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework. A temporary project-based composition has been established during the EOSC Future project, consisting of the task leads of the Architecture and Interoperability work package.
EOSC Interoperability Guideline Provider	Responsible for contributing and maintaining Interoperability Guidelines to the EOSC-IF Registry.
EOSC Observatory	An interactive dashboard to facilitate the monitoring of (1) EOSC readiness by European Member States and Associated Countries (2) indicators for the EOSC Partnership (3) contributions to the EOSC Partnership and EOSC ecosystem (4) national policies on Open Science and EOSC. The observatory will publicly present results of the monitoring and provide an overview of the implementation of EOSC.
EOSC Onboarding Strategy Group	Catalogue Operator Representatives for Community Catalogue from the INFRAEOSC-04-2018 (thematic projects), INFRAEOSC-05-2018-2019 (regional projects), and INFRAEOSC-07-2020 (horizontal projects) to ensure implementation/alignment of onboarding of Community catalogues; representatives of the EOSC Portal Onboarding Team (EPOT); operations and maintainer of the EOSC Profiles (led by Mark Dietrich) to ensure

	<p>implementation according to decisions made within the E-OSG are considered by the EOSC Provider's Portal developers. Other Provider Representatives interested in onboarding resources to the EOSC Resource Catalogue and EOSC Marketplace. Continuation of this group's activities, or a similar one, must be separately determined and resourced after EOSC Future finishes in March 2024.</p>
EOSC Marketplace	<p>A web-based interface to search, discover, access, order and use the resources available through the EOSC Exchange, exploiting a range of filtering options, leveraging the relationships available through the Interoperability Framework, and taking advantage of integrations with EOSC Core Services and among other compatible services in the EOSC Exchange.</p>
EOSC Partnership	<p>A Co-programmed European Partnership between the EOSC Association and European Commission to implement EOSC under Horizon Europe. The partnership is governed by the tripartite EOSC Partnership Board consisting of representatives from the EOSC Association, EOSC Steering Board, and European Commission. The European Commission will fund €490 million in project and procurement calls in the Work Programmes for EOSC under Horizon Europe. The EOSC Association will collectively via its members contribute in-kind activities to EOSC totaling minimally €500 million for the duration of Horizon Europe.</p>
EOSC Platform	<p>The EOSC Platform delivers EOSC Core services as an integrated operational environment that enables EOSC research communities to take advantage of this suite of Core services. Exploiting EOSC Platform capabilities, research communities can add value to their own services in the Exchange and make them more useful and attractive to a wider range of science users. Furthermore, the EOSC Platform, with its extensible architecture, facilitates the addition of new capabilities (Core or Exchange - e.g. horizontal services such as the data transfer) to satisfy emerging user's requirements. The EOSC Platform currently consists of services such as the comprehensive Resource Catalogues, the Marketplace, the EOSC Infrastructure Proxy for the EOSC Core services, the EOSC AAI Federation, the Helpdesk, the Monitoring, the Accounting, the Order Management, the Execution Framework and the EOSC Interoperability Framework registry.</p>
EOSC Portal	<p>A web-based interface to resources onboarded on the EOSC Marketplace and to a broader range of information and explanatory materials about all aspects of the EOSC Platform.</p>
EOSC Profile	<p>Metadata schemas for the description of services, research products or other research artefacts that their providers choose to share with the EOSC user community through the EOSC Exchange, as well as for describing the organisations offering to provide these resources to EOSC. EOSC Profiles are specified by the EOSC Profile Interoperability Guideline, which defines the entities for which Profiles have been defined and their logical relationships as part of a larger data model.</p>
EOSC Steering Board	<p>An expert group consisting of representatives of European Member States and Associated Countries that advises the European Commission in the development and implementation of EOSC. The board is also one of the three bodies in the tripartite EOSC Partnership Board that governs the EOSC Partnership.</p>
EOSC-Core	<p>Components of EOSC that provide the key internal capabilities - the 'glue' - to</p>

	support the basic operations of EOSC. This predominantly consists of services and resources which face service providers and the people coordinating EOSC.
EOSC Interoperability Guideline	Version-controlled documents that describe standards to enable interoperability and explain how Providers can make their resources compatible with them. They outline the high-level protocols (such as REST) and low-level protocols (such as OAI-PMH), data models (e.g. DCAT model), and schemas (e.g. DCAT JSON schema) that need to be implemented or customised to ensure compatibility with each guideline. Guidelines specify the essential technical requirements and configurations that providers should follow in order to make their services compatible with the interoperability guidelines. EOSC Interoperability Guidelines pass a validation process, after which they are onboarded (registered) into the EOSC IF registry.
EOSC-Core Interoperability Guideline	EOSC Interoperability guideline to enable compatibility with specific EOSC Core services, including EOSC monitoring, EOSC accounting, and EOSC helpdesk.
EOSC-Exchange	The collection of resources and organisations onboarded to the EOSC Platform, visible in the EOSC Resource Catalogue and EOSC Marketplace, and findable, accessible and usable by EOSC Users.
EOSC-Exchange Interoperability Guideline	EOSC-Exchange Interoperability Guidelines facilitate interoperation of services and resources within thematic areas. As such they are defined, proposed, and maintained by EOSC providers. Specifically, horizontal Interoperability Guidelines facilitate interoperation of services and resources across communities and infrastructures, and can communicate the interoperability capabilities and boundaries of frameworks utilised by communities.
EOSC-Interoperability Framework	The collection of EOSC Interoperability Guidelines onboarded to the EOSC Platform, visible in the EOSC IF Registry, which can be used to enable interoperability between individual EOSC Resources and EOSC Core services as well as interoperability between EOSC Resources (e.g. enabling data transfer, orchestration, etc.). The Framework includes the governance processes for reviewing, approving and accepting new Interoperability Guidelines into the IF Registry.
EOSC-Interoperability Framework Registry	A database of submitted and approved EOSC Interoperability Guidelines, based on an agreed profile of attributes.
EPOT	EOSC Portal Onboarding Team. The cross-project collaborative team which manages and operates the EOSC Onboarding and Audit processes to populate the EOSC-Exchange, using the EOSC Profiles and assessing the compliance of resources with the Inclusion Criteria derived from the EOSC Rules of Participation.
Horizontal Service	An EOSC Service that can be used in a general way to solve a broad class of problems and that should be used by two or more research infrastructures.
Hosting Legal Entity	A Hosting Legal Entity (HLE) is an institution registered as an EOSC resource provider, that is a legal entity and agrees to be accountable for resources onboarded to EOSC. Resources may be onboarded by a resource provider which is not a legal entity, but only if the Hosting Legal Entity field includes one legal entity already registered as resource provider, if this has been agreed in advance with them

Inclusion Criteria	A set of defined requirements with which providers, catalogue owners and resources need to comply in order to be onboarded into EOSC
Provider	An organisation operating a resource, whether operating a service or providing access to research artefacts, for use or access by users not affiliated with the organisation itself.
Research Product	A scientific or research output (classified as publication, i.e. literature, research data, research software, and "other kinds of products"), accessible or linked from an EOSC Data Source (e.g. repository, scientific database, publisher archive aggregator, CRIS system), whose metadata might be "harvested from" the linking EOSC Data Source using a defined protocol (such as OAI-PMH).
Resource	Services, catalogues, research products, training resources, interoperability guidelines and other assets. In the context of EOSC, these are understood to be both digital and produced or operated by, or of potential use to, scientists and researchers. Services include data sources, computational resources and data storage resources.
Rules of Participation (RoP)	The Rules of Participation (RoP) for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) state the standards and conduct required of EOSC participants. EOSC participants agree to adhere to the RoP.
Service	Digital system that allows a user either to interact with the system, entering data or other inputs, executing instructions through commands or other interfaces, or to issue machine-to-machine commands using a protocol such as an API that allows information or data to be supplied to the system, and that allows results to be received by the user through graphical interfaces and/or production of output data files.
Training resource	Any resource – including print and non-print materials and online/open-access resources – which supports and enhances, directly or indirectly, learning and teaching. If a training resource is used in a training environment, for training activities that are part of a training plan and involve instructors, facilitators and students, then we speak of training materials.

EOSC Future project Glossary is incorporated by reference: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/x/JOCK>

1 Introduction, Scope and Intended Audience

This EOSC Interoperability Guideline (IG) describes EOSC Profiles, which are metadata schemas for the description of services, research products or other research artefacts that their providers choose to share with the EOSC user community through the EOSC Exchange, as well as for describing the organisations offering to provide these resources to EOSC. Any provider or other responsible party (the “Provider” or the “Catalogue Operator”) that intends to include one or more research resources (“Resources”) in EOSC must describe each resource using the appropriate EOSC Profile, with Profile records for both themselves and those resources in the machine-readable digital formats described in this IG (see Section 2). Once described, the Provider or Catalogue Operator submits EOSC Profile records for processing following the procedures described in Section 10. If the processing is successful, the subject of each approved EOSC Profile record will be listed, findable and accessible in the EOSC Marketplace and can be integrated with other EOSC Core Services, pursuant to the respective EOSC IGs for those services. In this way EOSC Profiles ensure findability of information about any entity or resource within the system-of-systems framework of EOSC.

This document addresses the following specific audiences:

- Representatives (both technical and administrative) of Providers and/or Catalogue Operators that would like to onboard research resources under their control into EOSC (so that they are listed, findable and accessible in the EOSC Marketplace) and to potentially integrate with one or more EOSC Core Services.
- Individuals working with EOSC and related organisations on topics related to EOSC’s current and future architecture, design principles and broader questions of interoperability and governance.

More broadly, for EOSC to fulfil the vision of a federated system of systems, a strong and sustained partnership among the operators of the EOSC Platform and the research communities through the ESFRI Research Infrastructures (RIs) and related Science Clusters is essential. Within the EOSC Future project the key focus has been on the onboarding and integration of service and data source providers into the EOSC Marketplace. The RIs and the Science Clusters have been and are essential to this process. It is through them that outreach to and engagement of the research communities must be secured and sustained.

EOSC Profiles have several functions:

1. **Onboarding to EOSC:** EOSC Profile records include information needed to assess the compliance of a specific Provider, Catalogue Operator and/or Resource with the Rules of Participation¹ of EOSC, as well as the specific Inclusion Criteria² used by those responsible for onboarding such entities into the EOSC Exchange and monitoring their continued compliance with the Rules of Participation.
2. **Search, Display and Filter within EOSC:** EOSC Profile records include information needed to include the Provider and/or Resource³ in the EOSC Resource Catalogue (combining the EOSC Service Catalogue and EOSC Research Product Catalogue) and the EOSC Marketplace. Generally, a Provider or Resource is included (displayed) automatically in the EOSC Marketplace once it has been included in the EOSC Resource Catalogue.
3. **Integration with EOSC Core Services:** EOSC Profile records act as reference identifiers to support integration of any Resource with one or more EOSC Core Services, including EOSC Monitoring, EOSC Accounting, EOSC Helpdesk and EOSC Order Management. Specific integrations are detailed in various “extensions”, which are themselves described in the relevant Interoperability Guideline (IG) for the EOSC Core Service that uses an extension (see Section 7: Related Guidelines). Extensions are

¹

[https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/a96d6233-554e-11eb-b59f-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-184432576#:~:text=The%20Rules%20of%20Participation%20\(RoP,the%20resources%20accessible%20through%20EOSC](https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/a96d6233-554e-11eb-b59f-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-184432576#:~:text=The%20Rules%20of%20Participation%20(RoP,the%20resources%20accessible%20through%20EOSC)

² <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+Exchange+inclusion+criteria>

³ Note that in Version 5.0, Catalogue Operators and the catalogues they operate are NOT listed in the EOSC Marketplace.

not part of the EOSC Profile schema, but refer to the identifier of the corresponding EOSC Profile record. (Note that, in the abstract, function 2 above represents integration of a resource with the EOSC Resource Catalogue and the EOSC Marketplace, both of which are Core Services – but no specific “extension” is required for this, and this integration is the implicit purpose of the EOSC Profile itself.)

4. **Anchoring of capabilities in EOSC:** Certain EOSC Profiles enable a range of possible resources to be described, and specific Subprofiles are defined to enhance the three functions described above for a specific type of resource. At the time of writing, one Subprofile schema, for a Data Source, has been defined, enhancing the generic Service Profile schema. This Subprofile schema is documented below. Other subprofiles are planned for future implementation, particularly for Services that describe computational resources, and for Services that describe data storage resources.

This version of interoperability guidelines describes the particular version of the EOSC profile schemas created during the implementation of the EOSC Future project and reflects the architectural concepts based on the community inputs and expertise of the project partners at the time of implementation. It accumulates numerous changes in the profiles itself, and in the procedures for gathering the community input that have been agreed-upon by a wide group of stakeholders. EOSC concepts as well as the EOSC community have been experiencing rapid evolution during the last months of the EOSC Future project. Accumulation of the new demand and subsequent implementation of new versions of EOSC Profile schemas will have to be undertaken after the EOSC Future project finishes (see chapter 12 for potential directions).

2 Version History and Change Log

This document describes the EOSC Profile schemas specified in version 5.0 (V5.0), representing the “state of the art” of EOSC Profile schemas, and the nearly final instance of the Profile schemas as implemented by the EOSC Future project. EOSC Profiles V5.0 were fully released into production in the EOSC Future instance of EOSC (eoscfuture.eu) in November 2023. They are documented in GitHub here: <https://eosc-profiles.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.

2.1 Version History

Version 4.0 of the EOSC Profile schemas were implemented in phases over a period starting in June 2022, beginning with version 4.0 of the EOSC Profile schemas for Providers and Resources, which were updated from version 3.0, as well as the new EOSC Profile schema for Catalogues. One additional EOSC Profile schema was included in version 4.0: the Data Source Profile as a separate Profile schema, in September 2022, which had been contemplated in the original plan for version 3.0 of the Profiles.

Version 5.0 reflects a range of significant achievements by the EOSC Future project, including the following:

- March 2023, new Service Profile schema, mirroring the Resource Profile schema, but named “Service” to more clearly specify the entities represented by the Service Profile schema,
- March 2023, Training Resource Profile schema released into production,
- April 2023, Interoperability Guideline Profile schema released into production,
- November 2023, Data Source Profile schema integrated as “subprofile” of Service Profile schema.

Existing Profile schema specifications were kept unchanged as new Profile schemas were introduced, so versioning was maintained at 4.0 from March 2023 until the latest release. Since the latest release contemplates a breaking change (non backward-compatible change), version-numbers for all Profile specifications are incremented to the latest version. Documentation can be found at <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+Portal+Profiles>, but this documentation will be deprecated once both this Interoperability Guideline is accepted and the corresponding GitHub documentation is fully complete.

As new versions of EOSC Profile schemas are implemented, this Interoperability Guideline will be updated as needed. The GitHub documentation refers to the “latest” version of the Profile schemas (<https://eosc-profiles.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>), but also includes earlier versions starting with version 4.0.

2.2 Change Log for Version 5.0

Version 5.0 implements the following changes:

- EOSC Resource Profile schema was disabled in the Providers Portal in November 2023, and the Resource Profile API will be deprecated by March 2024.
- EOSC Service Profile schema was enhanced with 4 fields: *Service Category*, *Marketplace Location*, *Horizontal Service* and *PIDs*, which will become mandatory in March 2024 (version 5.1.0). Existing *Category* and *Subcategory* fields will be deprecated by March 2024.
- Some but not all provider suggestions for new values of Controlled Vocabularies are accepted. Some fields no longer allow suggestions of new controlled vocabulary values, since the vocabulary is reasonably broad or based on a standard reference.
- All records related to existing Data Sources have been migrated to conform to the new logical structure, where a Data Source record is a “subprofile” of a Service Profile record (based on its *Service Category*). In some cases, “parent” Service Profile records have been created by the technical teams to respect this logic, and respective Providers will need to review.

2.2.1 EOSC Resource Profile

The EOSC Resource Profile schema has been superseded by the EOSC Service Profile schema, which was introduced in June 2022. In Version 5.0.0, the EOSC Service Profile schema has been updated, while the EOSC Resource Profile will be deprecated in March 2024. Providers using the Resource Profile API should start using the Service Profile API, including the changes described here. Updated Swagger pages can be found here: <https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/openapi>, along with implementation instructions and information about a sandbox instance where Providers can test the Service Profile schema with their own data.

2.2.2 EOSC Service Profile

The EOSC Service Profile schema has been enhanced with several new fields:

- *Service Category* (accepting multiple selections from a controlled vocabulary)
- *Marketplace Location* (accepting multiple selections from a controlled vocabulary)
- *Horizontal Service* (Yes/No)
- *PIDs*.

In M30 (released November 2023, v5.0.0), these fields are optional but will become mandatory in M36 (March 2024, v5.1.0).

2.2.2.1 Service Category

The new *Service Category* field has four (4) possible values:

- “Data Source”
- “Compute”
- “Storage”
- “Other”.

This new field provides a simpler way of categorising services so that they can be more easily found by users in the EOSC Marketplace.

The new *Service Category* field has been automatically populated based on the current value(s) for each Service record in the *Category* field.

- All service records whose *Category* contains “Compute” or “Data Storage” had the *Service Category* field populated with “Compute” and/or “Storage” respectively.
- All other existing service records had “Other” set as the *Service Category*.

2.2.2.2 Marketplace Location

The new *Service Category* field has been complemented by another new field, *Marketplace Location*, which will allow each Provider to directly manage the placement of each of their services in the different sections of the EOSC Marketplace. The acceptable values for this field are as follows:

- "Find Instruments And Equipment"
- "Explore Other Research Catalogues"
- "Publish Research Outputs"
- "Access Training Material"
- "Access Research Infrastructures"
- "Find Supporting Services For EInfras"
- "Access Computing And Storage Resources"
- "Manage Research Data"
- "Process And Analyze"
- "Discover Research Outputs".

These values are defined by the EOSC Marketplace team – new values can be suggested by Providers through the Helpdesk, and as the EOSC Marketplace itself evolves, in consultation with both Providers and Users, new "marketplace locations" are possible and would be reflected in the vocabulary.

This new field has been automatically populated based on the current settings for most service records, which have been established by the EOSC Marketplace team. With the M30 release (November 2023, v5.0.0), this field is available for Providers to access, review and update as needed.

2.2.2.3 Horizontal Services

Horizontal services are defined as "a generic service or resource bringing significant value to two or more research infrastructures" (as agreed by the EOSC Technical Coordination Board December 2022). Onboarded Horizontal Services are more easily findable by users in the EOSC Marketplace.

While this field was initially created as an internal field, allowing the EOSC Portal Onboarding Team (EPOT) to designate appropriate services as "horizontal", this decision should be made by Providers themselves. Therefore this field is now exposed to Providers through inclusion in the Service Profile schema, implemented in both the user interface as well as the new Service Profile API, so that Providers can indicate their intent to provide certain services to a broad user base, and in turn making such services more easily findable in the EOSC Marketplace.

Any service records submitted that are marked with a "yes" in the *Horizontal Service* field will be reviewed by EPOT which must include sufficient domain expertise to confirm that the service aligns with the definition above.

2.2.2.4 Category and Subcategory

Prior to the current release (v5.0), *Category* and *Subcategory* allowed over one hundred values, which Providers attempted to specify, but this information proved too complicated to be useful to users in finding the resources they need. As described above, these fields have been replaced by the *Service Category* field. In March 2024, the *Category* and *Subcategory* fields will be deprecated.

2.2.2.5 PIDs

The Service Catalogue now mints PIDs internally for all resource records onboarded either directly or through third party catalogues. These PIDs are stored in the field *Identifiers*. For example, the public API exposing resources to EOSC Core components (i.e. elevated privileges), such as:

```
curl --location --request GET
'https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/api/public/service/adminPage/all?quantity=10000' --header 'Authorization: Bearer <token_here>'
```

returns services which contain an identifiers section.

For example, for service with id **csc-fi.csc_epouta**, the identifiers section looks like this:

```
"identifiers": {
  "alternativeIdentifiers": [
    {
      "type": "PID",
      "value": "7e960399"
    }
  ],
  "originalId": "csc-fi.csc_epouta"
},
```

PIDs that have already been minted by the providers for their resources are also included in the identifiers section as *alternativeIdentifiers*.

2.2.2.6 Controlled Vocabulary Changes for Provider and Service Profiles

Prior to the current release (v5.0), a number of fields linked to controlled vocabularies in the Service Profile and Provider Profile allowed Providers to suggest new values for these vocabularies when they selected “Other”. These suggestions have been reviewed – and several changes have been implemented as part of the new release:

In the EOSC Provider Profile schema:

- In the Provider's *Area of Activity*: new options are added: “Research Infrastructure”, “Publisher”, and “Social Network”. Selecting multiple values is allowed.
- For *Provider Legal Status*, several new options are added. Going forward, if an appropriate option does not seem to be available, Providers are encouraged to request additional values through helpdesk@eosc.eu.
- For *Provider Societal Grand Challenge*, we have added the individual possibilities from the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Selecting multiple values is allowed.
- For several fields (*Provider ESFRI Type*, *Provider Life Cycle Status*, *Provider MERIL Scientific Domain and Subdomain*, *Scientific Domain and Subdomain*), Providers are encouraged to find the value(s) that best match their situation, since the vocabularies are reasonably broad, or we are using vocabularies defined by other organisations. For some of these, selecting multiple values is now allowed.

In the EOSC Service Profile schema:

- *Access Mode* has been enhanced with another value “Free Initially, then Paid”. Otherwise Providers should be able to find appropriate values in the existing Vocabulary.
- *Funding Body* and *Funding Program* are expanded to include several suggestions, either as suggested or with edits. The “Other” choice remains for both fields, allowing Providers to make suggestions, but since the current vocabulary list is long we encourage Providers to try to find the value(s) that best match their situation before suggesting a new value. Providers also need to respect the difference between Funding Bodies and Funding Programmes. Funding Bodies are more persistent than Programmes, although we acknowledge, e.g., that the names of ministries sometimes change with new governments.
- *Target User* has been enhanced with several values: “Any”, “Citizens” and “Publishers”.

- For several fields (*Access Type, Order Type, Scientific Domain* and *Subdomain*), Providers are encouraged to find the value(s) that best match their situation, since the vocabularies are reasonably broad, or we are using vocabularies defined by other organisations. For some of these, selecting multiple values is now allowed.

2.2.3 EOSC Data Source Subprofile

Certain definitional and procedural changes have been implemented for the EOSC Data Source Subprofile, but this version introduces no changes to the Subprofile schema itself.

New technical logic has been implemented that links each Data Source Subprofile record to a related Service Profile record. These changes do not change the behaviour of the Data Source section of the Provider's Portal or of the related Data Source APIs.

In addition, the definition of a Data Source has been expanded [1] to allow the onboarding [2] of a variety of sources of data that would not have met the earlier original definitions for these resources, such as aggregators and CRIS systems.

It is now possible to onboard three categories of Data Sources:

- Data Sources that refer to or host research product resources that comply with the EOSC Research Product profile [3], and which can be harvested so that the individual research products are visible and can be searched in the Marketplace. Currently this requires the data source to be harvestable using one of several supported harvesting protocols [4], such as OAI-PMH.
- Data Sources that refer to or host research product resources that comply with the EOSC Research Product specification [3], but which can only be harvested using protocols that are NOT yet supported by EOSC. In this case, the research products will not be onboarded into the EOSC Resource Catalogue but will still be available to users via the access points defined for the Data Source.
- Data Sources that refer to other data assets that do NOT comply with the EOSC Research Product specification [3]. For example, many data sources provide one or more API interfaces to query and search for certain kinds of data, e.g. based on geographic location or biological taxonomy, with the API returning the selected data in chosen formats. While this data cannot be onboarded onto the EOSC Resource Catalogue, it is of course valuable to Users and available via the access points defined for the Data Source.

For categories 2 and 3, the Data Source Provider is encouraged to describe the harvesting protocols and API specifications that a user would need to use to query and search for the research resources they need. Ideally each of these protocols and specifications would be documented in an EOSC Interoperability Framework Guideline, which can then be linked with the Data Source Profile record to support increased interoperability and utility.

Relevant links:

1. [v4.00 EOSC Data Source Profile](#)
2. [EPOT Procedure-09: Onboard data source and research products](#)
3. [v4.00 EOSC Research Product Profile](#)
4. [EOSC Data Source protocols for Research Products Onboarding](#)

2.2.4 EOSC Catalogue Profile

New fields have been introduced for Catalogue Profile schemas, all related to basic information for the catalogue to be onboarded:

1. Description of the Catalogue scope: a short description of the purpose of the Catalogue as a collection of resources with specific characteristics of domain
2. URL for Inclusion Criteria: a link to the Inclusion Criteria used to populate the Catalogue
3. URL for Validation Process: a link to the document describing how validation is done and how the assessment against the Inclusion Criteria is performed

In the current release, these fields are optional but will become mandatory in M36 (March 2024, v5.1.0).

3 Description and main features

This section provides a high level description of all EOSC Profile schemas included in this Guideline and their relationships. In addition, this section describes the process for governance of the Profile schemas.

3.1 Taxonomy of EOSC Profile schemas and distinctive definitions

The following EOSC Profile “types” are covered by this document:

- Provider
- Catalogue
- Service
 - Data Source, as a Subprofile of Service
- Training Material
- Research Product
- Interoperability Guideline.

The Provider and Catalogue Profile schemas are specific instances of a more general, but still virtual, “organisational” description. The other Profile schemas, as well as to some extent also the Catalogue Profile schema, are specific instances of a more general, but still virtual, “Resource” description. These relationships are illustrated in Figure 2-1 below.

Figure 2-1: Logical Relationships Among Profiles and Subprofiles

The Profile schemas are discussed in more detail below, starting with the virtual descriptions of Organisations and Resources.

3.1.1 Organisational Profiles: Provider and Catalogue

The Provider Profile schema and Catalogue Profile schema both capture metadata describing the organisations providing various Resources, as well the organisation operating the Community Catalogue in question. The Catalogue Profile schema also contains metadata describing the Community Catalogue itself. We start by defining the scope of these entities in the context of EOSC:

- **Organisation:** "An organisation operating a scientific or research resource, including catalogues, services, research product or other research artefacts for use or access by users not affiliated with the organisation itself."
- **Provider:** "An organisation operating a resource, whether operating a service or providing access to research artefacts for use or access by users not affiliated with the organisation itself."
- **Catalogue Operator:** "An organisation operating an EOSC-compliant community catalogue and responsible for the onboarding and validating selected resources from that community catalogue into the EOSC Exchange."
- **Community Catalogue:** "A Community catalogue complying with EOSC-Exchange community resource catalogue inclusion criteria and including several resources. It is a Community Catalogue that can be onboarded into the EOSC Exchange by a Catalogue Operator Representative on behalf of the Community Catalogue Operator."

Detailed specifications can be found at the GitHub link referenced above, but common descriptive information required for organisations (Providers or Catalogue Operators) includes:

- Basic descriptive information
 - Organisation name
 - Abbreviation
 - Physical address
 - Description (marketing style)
 - Website, logo, multimedia assets about the organisation
 - Tags or keywords that could aid users searching for the organisation
- Structural information
 - Legal information (whether the organisation is a legal entity, if so its form and legal location, if not the legal entity taking responsibility for the organisation and its form and legal location)
 - Related organisations that together with the profiled organisation provide the resource for use
 - Architectural style of the organisation as a provider (single-sited, distributed, mobile, virtual)
- Contact details (names, emails, telephone, job roles/positions, etc.)
 - Public
 - Administrative. Note this contact is defined as the individual authorised to manage the related record in the EOSC Resource Catalogue.
 - Technical
 - Contact responsible for handling security incidents
- Relationships
 - Affiliated organisations
 - Networks of which the organisation is a member
 - Scientific roadmaps in which the organisation participates
 - Countries funding the organisation
- Categorisations
 - Areas of activity (e.g. basic research, research infrastructure, publisher)
 - Scientific domains and subdomains (based on the 2007 Frascati Manual)
 - Infrastructure categories (based on MERIL taxonomy)
 - ESFRI domains and type
 - Scientific grand challenges targeted by the organisation
- Qualitative information
 - Certifications
 - Life cycle status of the organisation

For a Community Catalogue itself:

- Name (of the Catalogue)
- Projected End of Life (addressing its sustainability)
- Inclusion Criteria (applied by the Catalogue, in comparison with the Rules of Participation and Inclusion Criteria defined by EOSC)
- Validation Process (description of the process for validating the contents of the Catalogue against its self-reported inclusion criteria)

3.1.2 Resource Profiles: Service, Data Source, Training Materials, Interoperability Guidelines

The Service, Data Source, Training Material and Interoperability Guideline Profile schemas all capture metadata describing different kinds of resources. We start by defining the scope of each of these entities in the context of EOSC:

- **Resource:** “Services, catalogues, research products, training resources, interoperability guidelines and other assets. In the context of EOSC, these are understood to be both digital and produced or operated by or of potential use to scientists and researchers. Services include data sources, computational resources and data storage resources.”
- **Service:** “Digital system that allows a user either to interact with the system, entering data or other inputs, executing instructions through commands or other interfaces, or to issue machine-to-machine commands using a protocol such as an API that allows information or data to be supplied to the system, and that allows results to be received by the user through graphical interfaces and/or production of output data files.”
- **Data Source:** “A service that links to collections of research products (see Research Product) as well as services that provide data in response to queries.”
- **Training Resources:** “Any resource – including print and non-print materials and online/open-access resources – which supports and enhances, directly or indirectly, learning and teaching. When a training resource is used in a training environment, for training activities that are part of a training plan and involve instructors, facilitators and students, we speak of training materials.”
- **Interoperability Guideline:** “Version-controlled document(s) that describe practices, protocols, standards, etc, to enable interoperability and explain how Providers can make their resources compatible with them. They outline the high-level protocols (such as REST) and low-level protocols (such as OAI-PMH), data models (e.g. DCAT model), and schemas (e.g. DCAT JSON schema) that need to be implemented or customised to ensure compatibility with each guideline. Guidelines specify the essential technical requirements and configurations that providers should follow in order to make their services compatible with the interoperability guidelines. EOSC Interoperability Guidelines pass a validation process, after which they are onboarded (registered) into the EOSC IF registry.”

Detailed specifications can be found at the GitHub link referenced above, but common information describing the “virtual” Resource includes:

- Basic descriptive information
 - Name/Title
 - Abbreviation
 - Description
 - Keywords or tags
 - Website, logo, multimedia assets about the resource, tagline
 - URL link to resource, URL type
 - Categories appropriate to the Profile Type
- Usage Information
 - Target (target user, domain, target groups)
 - Life cycle status, status

- Help desk page
- Geographic availabilities (which countries can access)
- Geographic locations (where resource is provided from)
- Language availabilities
- User Manual
- Training Information
- Use Case Name, Use Case
- Access mechanisms
 - Modes
 - Types
 - Policies
- Licences/rights
 - Licence type
 - Licence title
 - Licence URL
- Relationships
 - Catalogue from which this resource was onboarded
- Contacts distinct from Provider or Catalogue
 - Administrative. Note this contact is defined as the individual authorised to manage the related record in the EOSC Resource Catalogue.
 - Creator and Affiliation for Interoperability Guideline
 - Author(s) for Service
 - Helpdesk contact
 - Security contact
- Categorisations
 - Scientific domains and subdomains (based on the 2007 Frascati Manual)
 - Infrastructure categories (based on MERIL taxonomy)
 - Funding sources (funding bodies, projects)
- Qualitative information
 - Standards supported

For a Service itself:

- Ordering and Use
 - Ordering page (URL)
 - Order type
 - Payment model
 - Pricing
 - Privacy policy (URL)
 - Terms of Use (URL)
- Qualitative information
 - Certifications
 - Technological Readiness Level (TRL)
 - Description of functional updates since last version
 - Last update
 - Version
 - Maintenance information
 - Open source software supported
 - Monitoring status
 - Performance expectations
- Relationships
 - Related Resources
 - Related Platforms

For a Data Source itself:

- Content
 - Type
 - Jurisdiction
 - Thematic (Y/N)
 - Research Entity Types
- Policies
 - Submission Policy
 - Preservation Policy
 - Version Control
 - PID types

For a Training Resource itself:

- Duration of training
- Target skill level
- Learning outcomes
- Qualification received upon completion
- Version date.

For an Interoperability Guideline itself:

- Created date
- Publication date
- Last saved date
- Guideline type
- Integration options
- Identifier and type (e.g. DOI).

3.1.3 Research Products

Research Products are defined as: “a scientific or research output (classified as publication (literature), research data, research software, and “other kinds of products”), accessible or linked from an EOSC Data Source (e.g. repository, scientific database, publisher archive aggregator, CRIS system), whose metadata might be “harvested from” the linking EOSC Data Source using a defined protocol (e.g. OAI-PMH)”.

Note however that there is **no** EOSC Profile schema for a Research Product *per se*. This entity appears in Figure 2-1 as a virtual entity, which in turn refers to several specific kinds of Research Product, as defined by the latest Guidelines of OpenAIRE (<https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>). As of the date of this document, these guidelines recognize the following specifications for Research Products:

- **OpenAIRE Guidelines for Institutional and Thematic Repositories v4.0**
<https://openaire-guidelines-for-literature-repository-managers.readthedocs.io/en/v4.0.0>
- **OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories v3.0** (for resources onboarded in the OpenAIRE Graph before 1/1/2023) https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/literature/index_guidelines-lit_v3.html
- **OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives v2.0**
<https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/introduction.html>
- **OpenAIRE Guidelines for CRIS Managers v1.1**
<https://openaire-guidelines-for-cris-managers.readthedocs.io/en/v1.1.1/>

Research Products are present in the data model of the EOSC Platform, allowing data about Research Products of many kinds to be stored, processed and manipulated by the different components of the Platform. However these Research Products only appear in EOSC through indirect onboarding through the OpenAIRE system, described in more detail in section 11.5 below.

3.2 Profile Governance: Managing the Process to Change EOSC Profiles

EOSC Profile Governance is managed by the EOSC Profile Governance Group (EPGG), which in EOSC Future was identified as the team assigned to Task 3.2.1 in WP3. When the EOSC Future project finishes, in March 2024, this responsibility will need to be taken over by another group with appropriate resources. Candidates for this activity include the EOSC Association, the successful proponent for the Lot 1 Managed Services of EOSC Procurement (<https://etendering.ted.europa.eu/cft/cft-display.html?cftId=12087>), and the EOSC BEYOND Consortium (<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-info-ra-2023-eosc-01-04>), or some combination of these groups.

Profile schemas should be governed with the following principles in mind:

- The function(s) of each Profile, listed in section 1 above, should guide how the profiles evolve. Specifically each field in a given Profile specification should contribute to or support the listed functions.
- Where possible, profile specifications should take advantage of appropriate metadata schema created by other (larger, well-established) communities that contribute to the same objectives. In particular, if a specific field required in an EOSC Profile aligns with a very similar field described in another public schema, adopting the same definition as in the other profile helps to increase interoperability as well as comprehension of the Profiles by potential users. At the same time, if the purpose or scope of a candidate schema does not align with that of the desired EOSC Profile, this principle should not prevent EOSC from developing its own schema that is more “fit for purpose”.
- Providers and Catalogue Operators should be offered a balance between a) flexibility and autonomy in managing how their Resources are described and onboarded to EOSC and how they can be found and accessed through the EOSC Research Catalogue, and b) the administrative burden associated with creating and managing this process.
- Note that EOSC Profile schemas are NOT intended to define a “data model” for the information contained in the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace. While there are natural synergies and possible overlaps between these objectives, Profile schemas should only be expanded or modified in support of the discovery and findability objectives of EOSC.

Profile governance includes the following activities:

- Establishing and maintaining a version-controlled, publicly available specification of the EOSC Profile schemas.
- Gathering of possible changes to the EOSC Profile schemas, both from those involved in delivering the EOSC Platform and those in any scientific or research communities using the Platform.
- Debate and decision-making about proposed changes.
- Deciding on new version numbers.
- Documentation of approved changes.
- Changes to software, procedures or documentation in order to implement the approved Profile schema changes, and communicating these changes to the Providers (who will need to ensure they support changes that impact the content and/or manner in which their endpoints function in respect of the APIs).
- Validation of all software, procedures or documentation changes to confirm that they implement the changes to the Profile as they were approved.
- Updating of formal Profile schema specifications, including this Interoperability Guideline.

These activities are described below.

3.2.1 Establishing and maintaining a version-controlled, publicly available specification of the EOSC Profiles.

Over the course of multiple EU-funded projects that have been building components of EOSC and working to integrate these components into the EOSC Platform, various technologies have been used to document the EOSC Profiles, most recently a public “wiki” created for the EOSC Future project, using Confluence software hosted by EGI Foundation. Although this technology provides a platform suitable for disseminating the specifications publicly, it does not offer appropriate version-control capabilities or the ability to formally track proposed changes in a granular way.

Several alternative approaches and technologies were considered, and after assessment, GitHub was chosen as a widely accessible tool well suited to the requirements. GitHub was primarily created as a “website and cloud-based service that helps developers store and manage their code, as well as track and control changes to their code”, but is also well suited to managing formal specifications such as the EOSC Profile schemas. For the EOSC Profiles, a repository (<https://github.com/EOSC-PLATFORM>) has been created to hold the technical specifications of the Profiles.

To implement the specifications using GitHub, the EOSC Future project translated the specifications assembled in the EOSC Future “Wiki” into text files structured using the “RST” (“ReStructured Text”) format, which is widely used for technical documentation. This format is also compatible with a range of document generation tools, such as “ReadTheDocs”, which is used to translate the RST-formatted specifications into human-readable web pages, as well as PDFs for documentation, reporting and archiving purposes.

Specifically, each EOSC Profile schema has a corresponding RST file representing the Profile’s specification. In addition, each controlled vocabulary used by any field of the Profile schema has a specific RST file that documents the controlled vocabulary. These RST files are complemented with explanatory text for each profile in one or more descriptive files, also in RST format (e.g. “Introduction.RST”). This allows the complete specification, including details about each field of a profile, relevant controlled vocabularies, as well as narrative introductory and descriptive information, to be maintained in a version-controlled fashion, while also supporting generation of documentation artefacts using tools such as “ReadTheDocs”.

3.2.2 Collection of possible changes to the EOSC Profiles, proposed both by those involved in delivering the EOSC Platform and those in the communities using the Platform.

GitHub provides specific tools for its users to propose changes to the contents of a repository. The process requires the user to have an account on GitHub, so that the source of any changes can be identified. Certain members of the EPGG will be authorised to accept, reject or defer decision-making about proposed changes. Other identified users, mostly from the stakeholder community, can create their own “branches” of the main contents, reflecting the approved content and allowing the user to edit that content in the way that they propose. Each proposed change must be “committed” by the user (who is proposing the change) to their own branch of the contents. Once the user is satisfied with the changes that they have proposed, the user makes a “pull request” to signal that these changes should be “pulled” back into the main repository contents. At this point, authorised users (EPGG members) can review and discuss the proposed changes. If this discussion leads to approval, the Pull Request is accepted, is tagged to link the Pull Request with a release candidate (the next version of both the Profiles and their specification) and merged into the main content of the specification of EOSC Profile schemas. GitHub allows different versions of the documentation to be maintained so that past and planned releases are clearly documented.

For the EOSC Profile schemas, this generic capability of GitHub is used to manage the governance process as follows:

- The EOSC Profile Governance Group is identified and has the ability to comment on changes of others.
- The leader of the EPGG will receive rights in GitHub to accept Pull Requests and manage versions of the EOSC Profile schema specifications.
- Individuals interested in EOSC Profiles, e.g. representatives from linked EOSC Communities, can create accounts on GitHub and request the ability to create new branches in the EOSC Platform repository. This will allow them to make and commit changes to their branches, and then make Pull Requests for those changes, signalling their request for changes to the specifications.
- Other parties, such as members of the EOSC Portal Onboarding Team (EPOT) can make similar requests. In particular, EPOT is notified when Providers suggest new entries for controlled vocabularies, and e.g. one EPOT member could transcribe these requests into GitHub. (It may be possible to automate this.) Similarly, requests for changes may be reported through tickets in the EOSC Helpdesk, and these would be translated as Branches and Pull Requests in GitHub.
- The EPGG can itself initiate Pull Requests to address specific concerns or requirements.

⁴ <https://kinsta.com/knowledgebase/what-is-github/>

3.2.3 Decision-making about proposed changes.

Periodically and/or in response to operational pressures, the EPGG reviews Pull Requests submitted to the GitHub repository. The EPGG would then engage in dialog with requesting individuals to weigh the pros and cons of the requested change. The EPGG would decide whether to accept any requests and would assign them to specific release candidates in order to manage the implementation process.

3.2.4 Rules governing changes to version numbers.

Subject to practical experience, the following approach for releasing changes and changing version numbers will be followed:

- Major change: increment version by “1” and resetting the minor and patch numbers to zero (i.e. from 7.3.2 to 8.0.0):
 - Planned changes that are not backward compatible, for example where new information is mandatory in both the user interface of the Providers Dashboard as well as the updated Profile API. Such changes (not backward compatible) should be collected and implemented together to avoid changing major versions too often.
 - Planned reduction in cardinality from “1:m” to “1:1”.
 - Introduction of new Profile types.
 - Any other planned changes that require significant data migration in order to implement the new version of the Profile.
 - If agreed changes to any Profile are determined to be “major”, the full suite of Profiles should be treated as undergoing a major change, with corresponding version number changes) to ensure consistent testing and implementation across the full onboarding process.
 - Where new information will be required, related fields should be introduced as “optional” but with the version number incremented to reflect a major change. A subsequent “minor change” version can implement the already communicated transition to mandatory or other “breaking change”.
- Minor change: Increment version by “0.1” and resetting the patch number to zero (i.e. from 7.3.2 to 7.4.0):
 - Changes that introduce new but optional fields, or change a field from mandatory to optional.
 - Increase in cardinality from “1:1” to “1:m”.
 - Changes that require action by Providers or Catalogue Operators to review and update Profiles when values in Controlled Vocabularies are removed.
- Patch change: Increment version by “0.0.1” (i.e. from 7.3.1 to 7.3.2):
 - Changes in description of fields without changing the underlying semantics of those fields.
 - Additional value(s) in controlled vocabularies.

This Interoperability Guideline should be updated as needed to reflect new version numbers, along with corresponding change log information for both the Profile schema specifications themselves as well as any changes to the Guideline document. In many cases revised Profiles will not trigger changes to the text of this Guideline, but this should be clearly documented in each version.

3.2.5 Rules governing release cycle frequency

Changes to EOSC Profile schemas impact both Providers and Catalogue Operators, particularly those who use the APIs to submit and update information about their resources to the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace.

- Major changes (as defined in the preceding section) should be limited to once every 12 months in order to minimise the operational impact on Providers and Catalogue Operators. Implementing major changes more frequently should be avoided without there being a clear requirement for the change and clear benefits to affected parties.
- Similarly, minor changes (as defined in the preceding section) should be limited to once every 4 months in order to minimise the operational impact on Providers and Catalogue Operators.
- Patch changes can be implemented as needed.

In all cases, changes should be clearly documented with affected parties notified in advance, time should be provided to allow testing against the new version, and a period of time where both versions are supported may be required.

3.2.6 Documentation of approved changes.

GitHub would be used to document approved changes in each release, and depending on tools used by development teams, approved changes would be converted into Jira tickets or similar artefacts to support management and control of the change process.

3.2.7 Changes to software, procedures or documentation in order to implement the approved Profile changes.

Documented changes, which might apply to software, procedures as well as documentation for Providers and other stakeholders, would be implemented. For example, new software would be developed and deployed to a beta instance for testing.

The primary component of the EOSC Platform that implements the EOSC Profile schemas is the EOSC Service Catalogue, specifically the "Providers Portal". As an additional documentation artefact, the Providers Portal has the ability to generate XML Schema Description (XSD) files that reflect the "as is" state of the Profiles implementation. The developer of the Providers Portal has enhanced the programmatically generated schema details generated by the Providers Portal software with additional information, e.g. descriptions, cardinalities, optional/mandatory, etc. to ensure a complete representation of each implemented Profile and each field of that Profile.

When the Providers Portal is modified through the change management process and is deployed on beta, the updated XSD files generated by the Providers Portal can be compared to the change documentation in GitHub to ensure correct implementation of approved changes.

3.2.8 Validation of all software, procedures or documentation changes to confirm that they implement the changes to the Profile that were approved.

New artefacts (software in beta, revised procedure documentation, other documentation, as well as the XSD generated by the EOSC Providers Portal) would be reviewed by the EPGG to confirm correct behaviour of any new capabilities related to revised Profiles.

If new behaviour matches the new requirements, the EPGG would advise that the Profile-related changes are ready for release into production. If not, developers and those responsible for other artefacts would be asked for additional effort to align the new "as is" behaviour with the approved "to be" specification.

3.2.9 Updating of formal Profile specifications, including this Interoperability Guideline.

Once revised Profile implementations are deployed to production, the corresponding candidate release in GitHub can be updated to reflect that it is live.

Note that external references and URLs for the GitHub instance of the specifications should be sure to refer to the "latest" release so that these references will remain valid after each release.

4 Response to Community Need

EOSC aspires to enable the sharing of scientific and research resources across different scientific and research communities, and specifically to allow specific communities to share resources they have created with the broader scientific community. EOSC Profile schemas formalise this sharing process by defining the information needed to establish whether any given resource is appropriate for sharing across EOSC, as well as the information to make that resource "findable" by different communities. The resources described by EOSC Profiles can be enhanced with Extensions that enable integration with various EOSC Core Services, as well as with links to other Interoperability Guidelines (similar to this one) to add value through composability, orchestration and joint execution.

EOSC Profiles play a role in making scientific and research resources FAIR, primarily by enabling the onboarding of Resources to EOSC, where they are included in the EOSC Exchange and enable FINDABILITY

throughout EOSC. As noted above, “extensions” (described in other IGs) enable INTEROPERABILITY with various EOSC Core Services, and links between EOSC Profile records and relevant IGs also enable INTEROPERABILITY with other resources in the EOSC Exchange.⁵

5 High-level Service Architecture

Figure 4-1 illustrates the architectural links between the resources under the control of a Provider with the various components of the EOSC Platform that are relevant to the interoperability of the Provider’s resources with the EOSC Platform.

The following links (coloured orange in Figure 4-1) are critical:

- The Provider (lower left) interacts with the EOSC Service Catalogue to “Onboard Resources to increase their visibility and enhance their value to Customers”. This is accomplished through two interfaces:
 - User interface in Providers Portal (part of the EOSC Service Catalogue) (for Profile Types other than Research Products)
 - API interface to Providers Portal (for Profile Types other than Research Products)
- If the onboarded Resource is a Data Source:
 - The Service Catalogue and Research Product Catalogue synchronise information about the Data Source.
 - The Research Product Catalogue harvests individual Research Products where possible.
- The Provider also interacts with the EOSC Research Product Catalogue to “Onboard Research Products to increase their visibility and enhance their value to Customers”. This is accomplished through two interfaces:
 - User interface in Research Providers Portal (for Research Products)
 - API interface to Research Providers Portal (for Research Products)
- The Onboarding Workflow System scans the Service Catalogue for new information, alerting EPOT about new information so they can process new applications and audit compliance, in turn allowing EPOT to administer registered catalogue information.
- The Service Catalogue communicates approved registry applications to the EOSC Marketplace so that described resources are discoverable there.

⁵ ACCESSIBILITY is initially enabled by the EOSC AAI Federation, and the access of both a user and a resource provider with the EOSC AAI Federation, or, barring this, participation in a common AAI scheme. ACCESSIBILITY is also enabled by specific Extensions required for the EOSC Order Management System, which can be enhanced to implement conditions of access, licensing, access type, modes and limits, etc., as well as reflecting attributes and credentials of the user, to the extent this information is provided by one or more AAI (aka Trust & Identity) schemes. REUSABILITY is also a condition of use, which would initially be enabled by the EOSC Order Management System as well as the other mechanisms mentioned.

Figure 4-1: Architectural Links between Providers and Provider Resources with the EOSC Catalogue & Marketplace

6 Definitions

See "Glossary" above.

7 Licensing Information

This guideline and related specifications are made available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (<https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.html>) ("CC-BY-4.0").

8 Related Guidelines

As the "anchors" for nearly all capabilities in EOSC, EOSC Profile schemas can be expected to be related to nearly all current and future EOSC Interoperability Guidelines (IGs).

The table below lists specific IGs that enable integration of EOSC Profile records with one or more EOSC Core Services. Entities described by EOSC Profile records are not required to comply with any other EOSC IGs, although such compliance enables greater integration with EOSC Core Services, increases FAIRness, and contributes to increased use of the compliant resources.

Table 8-1: Related Guidelines

Resource Type	Title	Short Description	Link to IG
Service Profile	EOSC AAI Federation	Participation of the Provider of a Service in the EOSC AAI	<url>

		Federation increases the ACCESSIBILITY of the Service.	
Service Profile	EOSC Monitoring	Extension enables integration with EOSC Monitoring, allowing collection of service availability and reliability data using formats and protocols consistent with those used for other services available through EOSC. This increases the RE-USABILITY of the Service.	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7118590
Service Profile	EOSC Accounting for Services	Extension enables integration with EOSC Accounting for Services, allowing collection of service usage data using formats and protocols consistent with those used for other services available through EOSC. This increases the RE-USABILITY of the Service.	<i>Forthcoming</i>
Service Profile	EOSC Order Management	Extension enables integration with EOSC Order Management System, allowing users to specify, request and order services available through EOSC using consistent and comparable mechanisms. This increases the ACCESSIBILITY of the Service.	<i>Forthcoming</i>
Research Product	EOSC Research Product Profile	Compliance of a Research Product with this IG enables it to be harvested into the EOSC Research Product Catalogue, which in turn allows it to be included and FINDABLE within the EOSC Resource Catalogue and the EOSC Marketplace. This increases the FINDABILITY of each Research Product.	https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/E.+v4.00+EOSC+Research+Product+Profile
Data Source	EOSC Accounting for Research Products	Extension enables integration with EOSC Accounting for Research Products, allowing collection of research product access, citation and usage data using formats and protocols consistent with those used for other research products available through EOSC. This increases the RE-USABILITY of the Research Product.	https://zenodo.org/records/8362353
Data Source	EOSC-IF Interoperability Guidelines for Data Sources to onboard Research Products	Compliance of a Data Source with this IG enables the Research Products accessible from this Data Source to be harvested into the EOSC Knowledge Graph, which in turn allows them to be included and FINDABLE within the EOSC Marketplace. This increases the	https://zenodo.org/records/8362321

		FINDABILITY of these Research Products.	
Data Source	EOSC Data Source Profile	Data sources are EOSC Resources and a subclass of EOSC Services whose specific purpose is to offer deposition, preservation, curation, discovery, access, and usage statistics functionalities to collections of EOSC Research Products from a thematic or cross-discipline perspective.	https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/D.+v4.oo+EOSC+Data+Source+Profile

9 Adopted Standards

As described in Section 2, several fields of each EOSC Profile schema refer to controlled vocabularies created by other efforts and organisations. In general, these vocabularies have been selected because they represent expert opinion about subjects beyond the expertise of the EOSC Future project. For example EOSC Profile schemas use the updated (2007) Frascati Manual⁶ for a taxonomy of scientific and research disciplines as a definitive source, while recognizing that science and its disciplinary divisions will continue to evolve. This taxonomy, and most of the other externally sourced vocabularies, are not intended to be normative or limiting, but at the same time EOSC is not qualified to update these taxonomies.

The EOSC Interoperability Guideline profile's data model was based on the Data Cite Metadata Scheme v4.4⁷.

10 Integration Options

EOSC Profile schemas are the means by which resources (and their Providers or Catalogue Operators) are integrated with (i.e. "onboarded to") the EOSC Resource Catalogue and are then listed, findable and accessible in the EOSC Marketplace, which are the relevant "target" Core Services for this integration.

Descriptions of entities to be onboarded to EOSC, compliant with the appropriate EOSC Profile specification, can be created and submitted through two mechanisms:

- The user interface of the Providers Portal, a component of the EOSC Resource Catalogue, accessible here with recognized EOSC AAI credentials : <https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/provider/add>.
- Using the appropriate REST API interface for the Profile Type, all of which are defined in Swagger format here: <https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/openapi>. These APIs are also interfaces to the EOSC Resource Catalogue.

Providers and Catalogue Operators must select appropriate Profile schemas to describe their resources (and themselves) and present the information required for that Profile (as summarised in Section 2 above), using either manual data entry through the user interface or programmatically through the REST API calls described at the Swagger link above.

11 Interoperability Guidelines

Onboarding is the process by which the interoperability of a specific entity under the control of a Provider or Catalogue Operator is established with the EOSC Resource Catalogue and EOSC Marketplace. These processes are presented in this section in a logical order, proceeding from the onboarding of a Provider or Community Catalogue Operator through to the onboarding of specific Resources under their control.

⁶ www.oecd.org/sti/inno/38235147.pdf

⁷ Data Cite Metadata Schema 4.4, 201 [online] Available at: DataCite Metadata Working Group. (2021). DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs. Version 4.4. DataCite e.V. <https://doi.org/10.14454/3W3Z-SA82>.

11.1 Onboarding a Provider

Before starting onboarding resources into the EOSC Exchange, the Provider responsible for the resources needs to be onboarded. Figure 10-1 describes the onboarding process of a Provider.

Figure 10-1: Onboarding a Provider into the EOSC Exchange

Figure 10-1 illustrates the following steps:

1. Provider -> Service Catalogue: Provider Logs in to Service Providers Portal (UI for Service Catalogue), Completes Provider Profile, Submits for Review via Onboard Resources to increase their visibility and enhance their value to Consumers

2. Service Catalogue -> Onboarding Workflow system: Pending Provider Profile flagged for Validation by EPOT via Onboarding Workflow System scans for pending information in Service Catalogue
3. EPOT -> Onboarding Workflow system: EPOT advised of new Provider Profile via EPOT uses Onboarding system to process new applications and audit compliance
4. EPOT -> Onboarding Workflow system: EPOT approves new Provider via EPOT uses Onboarding system to process new applications and audit compliance
5. EPOT -> Service Catalogue: Update Status of Provider in Service Catalogue via EPOT Administers Registered Service Catalogue Information
6. Service Catalogue -> Marketplace: Make Service Provider visible in Marketplace via Service Catalogue Updates information in Marketplace
7. Marketplace -> Resource Discovery: Service Provider information is exposed for Discovery via Resource information from Marketplace updates Resource Discovery
8. Consumer -> Resource Discovery: Provider is visible to Consumer via Discover and Access Resources Enhanced by the EOSC Platform

11.2 Onboarding a Community Catalogue Operator and Resources from a Community Catalogue

A Community Catalogue is an EOSC-compliant catalogue offering services from multiple providers to its own target audience (e.g. International/National/Institutional and/or Thematic). The difference between a Provider and a Community Catalogue is that the Community Catalogue Operator (CCO) has no ownership of the services made available through its catalogue, similar to the resources made available through the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace. To make the services available through the EOSC Exchange, the CCO onboards itself to EOSC in order to onboard the services and data sources from its own catalogue into the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace.

EOSC Catalogue Onboarding Agreement

Just like Providers, CCOs are responsible for ensuring the services and data sources onboarded comply with the EOSC Inclusion Criteria. To ensure this compliance the CCOs need to agree with the EOSC Catalogue Onboarding Agreement. This is recorded through a check box in the EOSC Catalogue Profile.

The CCO acknowledges agreement to the minimum requirements for records operated by the CCO that will be specifically onboarded into the EOSC Resource Catalogue and that are specified in the EOSC-Exchange Inclusion Criteria, which are:

- To have a documented and methodical approach for the validation of information about resources that have been included in CCO's own catalogue.
- To ensure that records are kept up-to-date and that providers are prepared to correct errors if and when they are identified during the verification (auditing) procedures of EOSC Resource Catalogue records.
- To onboard and synchronise records with the EOSC Resource Catalogue.
- To cooperate with the operators of the EOSC Portal⁸ in ensuring that policies across catalogues are consistent by participating in the EOSC Onboarding Strategy Group (E-OSG).
- To follow the EOSC Security Operational Baseline⁹, as implemented by EOSC Future.

Community Catalogue onboarding process

To onboard the services and data sources from the Community Catalogue, the CCO needs to onboard the Community Catalogue as a Catalogue via the Providers Dashboard of the Service Catalogue. The onboarding process is illustrated in Figure 10-2.

⁸ <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

⁹ See section EOSC Security Operational Baseline

Figure 10-2: Onboarding resources from a Community Catalogue into the EOSC Exchange

Figure 10-2 illustrates the following steps:

1. Provider Exchange Service -> Community Catalogue: Onboard services from thematic/regional/national providers into the own catalogue via Onboard Service in Community Catalogue

2. Community Catalogue Operator -> Community Catalogue: Community Catalogue Operator validates the onboarded services according to the validation criteria of the own catalogue. via Validate onboarded Resources
3. Provider Exchange Data Source -> Community Catalogue: Onboard data sources from thematic/regional/national providers into the own catalogue via Onboard Data Source in Community Catalogue
4. Community Catalogue Operator -> Community Catalogue: Community Catalogue Operator validates the onboarded data sources according to the validation criteria of the own catalogue. via Validate onboarded Resources
5. Community Catalogue Operator -> Service Catalogue: Community Catalogue Operator Logs in to Service Providers Portal (UI for Service Catalogue), Completes Catalogue Profile, Submits for Review via Onboard Community Catalogue
6. Service Catalogue -> Onboarding Workflow system: Pending Catalogue Profile flagged for Validation via Onboarding Workflow System scans for pending information in Service Catalogue
7. Onboarding Workflow system -> EPOT: Onboarding Workflow system notifies EPOT team of new onboarding request via onboarding-team mailinglist via EPOT uses Onboarding system to process new applications and audit compliance
8. EPOT -> Service Catalogue: EPOT validates new Catalogue profile on basis of the EOSC Inclusion Criteria for Community Catalogues via EPOT Administers Registered Service Catalogue Information
9. EPOT -> Community Catalogue Operator: EPOT team provides feedback on the catalogue profile to the new Community Catalogue Operator via Email exchange
10. Community Catalogue Operator -> Service Catalogue: Community Catalogue Operator updates Catalogue profile on basis of given feedback via Onboard Community Catalogue
11. Community Catalogue Operator -> EPOT: Community Catalogue Operator sends email response to EPOT team with requested information via Email exchange
12. EPOT -> Onboarding Workflow system: EPOT approves new Catalogue in Onboarding Workflow system via EPOT uses Onboarding system to process new applications and audit compliance
13. EPOT -> Service Catalogue: After positive validation, the new Catalogue is approved, and Community Catalogue Operator is informed. via EPOT Administers Registered Service Catalogue Information
14. Service Catalogue -> Community Catalogue Operator: Service Catalogue sends email to Community Catalogue Operator with approved status via Inform Community Catalogue Operator with updates
15. Community Catalogue -> Service Catalogue: Test onboarding of resources from the new Catalogue on beta Service Catalogue via Register Resources in Service Catalogue
16. Community Catalogue -> Service Catalogue: After successful testing, start onboarding of resources into production Service Catalogue via Register Resources in Service Catalogue
17. EPOT -> Service Catalogue: Audit and approve onboarded providers and resources from the new Catalogue. Providers and resources from new Catalogues are audited via the same procedures as for directly onboarded Providers and Resources and need to comply with the same Inclusion Criteria via EPOT Administers Registered Service Catalogue Information
18. Service Catalogue -> Marketplace: Make onboarded Providers and Resources from the new Catalogue visible in Marketplace via Service Catalogue Updates information in Marketplace
19. Marketplace -> Resource Discovery: Provider and Resource information from new Catalogue is exposed for Discovery via Resource information from Marketplace updates Resource Discovery
20. Consumer -> Resource Discovery: Provider and resources from new Catalogue is visible to Consumer via Discover and Access Resources Enhanced by the EOSC Platform

11.3 Onboarding Services

Before onboarding Services, the Provider itself needs to be onboarded (see section 10.1).

The onboarding process of Services is split into two approaches:

1. Onboarding of the first Service
2. Onboarding of additional Services

These two approaches reflect the auditing process of the EOSC Portal Onboarding Team (EPOT). During the onboarding process of the first Service, EPOT will review and approve the description of the service submitted for consideration. After onboarding the first service, the Provider is assumed to understand the requirements,

and additional onboarded services will only be reviewed during periodic auditing activities, making the onboarding process more efficient for Providers.

11.3.1 Onboarding the first Service

The first Service is submitted manually by the Provider via the Provider Dashboard of the Service Catalogue. Figure 10-3 illustrates the onboarding process of the first service of a Provider in the EOSC Exchange.

Figure 10-3: Onboarding a Provider's first Service into the EOSC Exchange

Figure 10-3 illustrates the following steps:

1. Provider -> Service Catalogue: Service Provider Logs in to Service Providers Portal (UI for Service Catalogue), Completes Resource (Service) Profile, Submits for Review via Onboard Resources to increase their visibility and enhance their value to Consumers
2. Service Catalogue -> Onboarding Workflow system: If First Resource, Pending Resource Profile flagged for Validation by EPOT via Onboarding Workflow System scans for pending information in Service Catalogue
3. EPOT -> Onboarding Workflow system: If First Resource, EPOT Validates and approves new Resource (Service) Profile via EPOT uses Onboarding system to process new applications and audit compliance
4. EPOT -> Onboarding Workflow system: EPOT validates and approves 1st resource via EPOT uses Onboarding system to process new applications and audit compliance
5. EPOT -> Service Catalogue: Update Status of Resource (Service) in Service Catalogue via EPOT Administers Registered Service Catalogue Information
6. Service Catalogue -> Provider: Send Success Email to Service Providers via Emails to Service Providers
7. Service Catalogue -> Marketplace: Make Service visible in Marketplace via Service Catalogue Updates information in Marketplace
8. Marketplace -> Resource Discovery: Service information is exposed for Discovery via Resource information from Marketplace updates Resource Discovery
9. Consumer -> Resource Discovery: Service is visible to Consumer via Discover and Access Resources Enhanced by the EOSC Platform

11.3.2 Onboarding Additional Services

Additional Services can also be onboarded manually or programmatically through the PROVIDER PORTAL REST API¹⁰. Manual onboarding (using the Provider Dashboard of the Service Catalogue) follows the process illustrated in Figure 10-3 above, eliminating steps 3-5 in the listing above.

Onboarding additional services using the Provider Portal REST API is illustrated in Figure 10-4 below:

¹⁰ <https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/developers>

Figure 10-4: Onboarding Service into the EOSC Exchange using the Service Profile API

Figure 10-4 illustrates the following steps:

1. Provider Service Catalogue -> Service Catalogue: Provider Service Catalogue presents new or updated Resource (Service) Profile to Service Catalogue using the API, first using the VALIDATE call, then when the Profile is successfully validated, using the POST call. via Onboard Services/Data Source to Service Catalogue
2. Service Catalogue -> Onboarding Workflow system: If First Resource, Pending Resource Profile flagged for Validation by EPOT via Onboarding Workflow System scans for pending information in Service Catalogue
3. EPOT -> Onboarding Workflow system: If First Resource, EPOT Validates and approves new Resource (Service) Profile via EPOT uses Onboarding system to process new applications and audit compliance
4. EPOT -> Onboarding Workflow system: EPOT validates and approves 1st resource via EPOT uses Onboarding system to process new applications and audit compliance
5. EPOT -> Service Catalogue: If First Resource, Update Status of Resource (Service) in Service Catalogue via EPOT Administers Registered Service Catalogue Information
6. Service Catalogue -> Provider Service Catalogue: Return Success to Provide Service Catalogue via Onboard Services/Data Source to Service Catalogue
7. Service Catalogue -> Marketplace: Make Service visible in Marketplace via Service Catalogue Updates information in Marketplace
8. Marketplace -> Resource Discovery: Service information is exposed for Discovery via Resource information from Marketplace updates Resource Discovery
9. Consumer -> Resource Discovery: Service is visible to Consumer via Discover and Access Resources Enhanced by the EOSC Platform

11.4 Onboarding Data Sources

Before onboarding Research Products, the Service containing the research products and/or making the metadata descriptions of the research products available, must be onboarded as a Data Source. As with a Service, the onboarding of Data Sources is split into two approaches, one for the first Data Source, and later for all subsequent Data Sources.

11.4.1 Onboarding the First Data Source

Figure 10-5 illustrates the onboarding process of the first Data Source of a Provider in the EOSC Exchange.

Figure 10-5: Onboarding a Provider's first Data Source into the EOSC Exchange

Figure 10-5 illustrates the following steps:

1. Provider -> Service Catalogue: Provider Logs in to Service Providers Portal (UI for Service Catalogue), Completes Data Source Profile, Submits for Review via Onboard Resources to increase their visibility and enhance their value to Consumers
2. Service Catalogue -> Research Product Catalogue: Service Provider selects matching Data Source from list of all Data Sources already onboarded in Research Product Catalogue (list can be searched). Service Provider completes information not available from Research Product Catalogue via Service Catalogue Gets Data Sources from Research Product Catalogue
3. Service Catalogue: If Data Source does not exist in Research Product Catalogue, Provider completes all information required
4. Service Catalogue -> Onboarding Workflow system: If First Resource, Pending Data Source Profile flagged for Validation by EPOT via Onboarding Workflow System scans for pending information in Service Catalogue
5. EPOT -> Onboarding Workflow system: If First Resource, EPOT Validates and approves new Data Source Profile via EPOT uses Onboarding system to process new applications and audit compliance
6. EPOT -> Service Catalogue: EPOT Approves new Data Source via EPOT Administers Registered Service Catalogue Information

7. Service Catalogue -> Onboarding Workflow system: Update Status of Data Source in Service Catalogue via Onboarding Workflow System scans for pending information in Service Catalogue
8. Service Catalogue -> Marketplace: Make Data Source visible in Marketplace via Service Catalogue Updates information in Marketplace
9. Marketplace -> Resource Discovery: Data Source information is exposed for Discovery via Resource information from Marketplace updates Resource Discovery
10. Consumer -> Resource Discovery: Data Source is visible to Consumer via Discover and Access Resources Enhanced by the EOSC Platform

11.4.2 Onboarding Additional Data Sources

Additional Data Sources can also be onboarded manually or programmatically through the PROVIDER PORTAL REST API for Data Source Profiles. Manual onboarding (using the Provider Dashboard of the Service Catalogue) follows the process illustrated in Figure 10-5 above, eliminating steps 5-6 in the listing above.

Onboarding additional services using the Provider Portal REST API for Data Sources is similar to that illustrated in Figure 10-4 above.

11.5 Onboarding Research Products

Research Products are not onboarded directly into the EOSC Exchange. Instead Providers onboard their Data Sources (see section 11.4 above) to both the EOSC Service Catalogue and the Research Product Catalogue, and the Provider establishes the link between them. If the Data Source links to Research Products that can be harvested by the harvesting protocols supported by EOSC, harvested Research Products will be added to the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace, linked to the corresponding Data Source, and will then be discoverable and usable by EOSC Users. Figure 10-6 describes this process for Research Products.

Figure 10-6: Onboarding Research Products into the EOSC Exchange

Figure 10-6 illustrates the following steps:

1. Provider -> Service Catalogue: Onboard Provider Exchange Data Source as Data Source into the Service Catalogue (using either UI or API via Provider Service Catalogue) [see separate process Flows] via Onboard Resources to increase their visibility and enhance their value to Consumers
2. Service Catalogue -> Research Product Catalogue: Data Source Provider links to onboarded Data Source in Research Product Catalogue and triggers validation/harvesting of Data Source via Service Catalogue Gets Data Sources from Research Product Catalogue
3. Research Product Catalogue -> Provider Exchange Data Source: Research Product Catalogue harvests individual Research Products using supported harvesting standards
4. Provider -> Research Product Catalogue: Manage Research Product onboarding process via the Research Product Catalogue Provide Dashboard via Onboard Research Products to increase their visibility and enhance their value to Consumers
5. Research Product Catalogue: Harvested Research Products are validated against FAIR metrics
6. Research Product Catalogue -> Explore: Newly harvested and validated Research Products are visible in Explore via Research Product Catalogue Updates Explore

7. Explore -> Resource Discovery: Newly harvested Research Products are visible in Resource Discovery via Research Product Information from Explore updates Resource Discover
8. Consumer -> Resource Discovery: Research Products are visible to Consumer via Discover and Access Resources Enhanced by the EOSC Platform

11.6 Onboarding Training Materials

Before onboarding Training Materials, the Provider itself needs to be onboarded (see section 10.1).

The onboarding process of Training Materials is split into two approaches:

1. Onboarding of the first Training Material
2. Onboarding of additional Training Materials.

These two approaches reflect the auditing process of the EOSC Portal Onboarding Team (EPOT). During the onboarding process of the first Training Material, EPOT will review and approve the description of the training material submitted for consideration. After onboarding the first training material, the Provider is assumed to understand the requirements, and additional onboarded training materials will only be reviewed during periodic auditing activities, making the onboarding process more efficient for Providers.

The first Training Material is submitted manually by the Provider via the Provider Dashboard of the Service Catalogue. The process and individual steps are the same as for Services, illustrated in Figure 10-3.

Subsequent Training Materials can also be submitted manually by the Provider, using a similar process to that illustrated for Services in Figure 10-3 (eliminating the EPOT steps). Onboarding additional Training Materials using the Provider Portal REST API for the EOSC Training Material Profile API is similar to that illustrated for Services in Figure 10-4.

11.7 Onboarding Interoperability Guidelines

Before onboarding Interoperability Guidelines, the Provider itself needs to be onboarded (see section 10.1).

The onboarding process of Interoperability Guidelines is split into two approaches:

1. Onboarding of the first Interoperability Guideline
2. Onboarding of additional Interoperability Guidelines.

These two approaches reflect the auditing process of the EOSC Portal Onboarding Team (EPOT). During the onboarding process of the first Interoperability Guideline, EPOT will review and approve the description of the guideline submitted for consideration. After onboarding the first guideline, the Provider is assumed to understand the requirements, and additional onboarded guidelines will only be reviewed during periodic auditing activities, making the onboarding process more efficient for Providers.

The first Interoperability Guideline is submitted manually by the Provider via the Provider Dashboard of the Service Catalogue. The process and individual steps are the same as for Services, illustrated in Figure 10-3.

Subsequent Interoperability Guidelines can also be submitted manually by the Provider, using a similar process to that illustrated for Services in Figure 10-3, with the EPOT review steps still applied. Onboarding additional Interoperability Guidelines using the Provider Portal REST API for the EOSC Interoperability Guideline Profile API is similar to that illustrated for Services in Figure 10-4.

12 Examples of solutions implementing this specification

As of 6/12/2023, the production instances of the EOSC Resource Catalogue and EOSC Marketplace include the following counts of each EOSC Profile type:

Table 12-1: Profile Records Implementing This Specification

Profile	EOSC Resource Catalogue	EOSC Marketplace ¹¹
Providers	393	329
Services	614	469
Datasources	72	71
Training Resources	25	24
Interoperability Guidelines	25	24
Catalogues	14	3

13 Evolution and Development

This version of the EOSC Profile schemas has been developed and implemented by the EOSC Future project, which will finish in March 2024. A follow-up technical development project, EOSC BEYOND will start in April 2024 and run through March 2027. In parallel, managed services to operate the EOSC Platform, using the EOSC Profile schemas and related governance procedures, are now being procured by the European Commission under tender (<https://etendering.ted.europa.eu/cft/cft-display.html?cftId=12087>), with services expected to be available from mid 2024 through mid 2027. These initiatives will have to take over and may decide to advance at least some of the operational aspects described in these guidelines. Overall governance of the development of the EOSC profiles beyond the EOSC Future project has to be decided outside the scope of that project.

The EOSC Profile schemas are a mechanism to describe the diversity of research artefacts and resources onboarded into the EOSC-Exchange, ensuring their findability and accessibility throughout the entire ecosystem.. The EOSC Profile schemas themselves shall evolve to reflect the expanding universe of such artefacts and resources, adapting to the changes of architectural concepts of the EOSC architecture, as well as developments among the specific EOSC community of practice (including regional and thematic catalogues, RIs, and other entities, e.g. industrial research). At the same time EOSC Profile schemas must always be clear and practical to enable findability and accessibility.

Future evolution and development will be driven by the necessity to fulfil the purpose of the EOSC Profile schemas in the evolving environment of the EOSC Architecture and the EOSC Platform. Specific developments can be expected in several areas:

- Refining profiles to remove or simplify data requested that is not used or used fully.
- Adding data that would improve usability (in connection with the four functions listed in section 1).
 - E.g. adding fields to enable automated assessment of inclusion criteria vs. requiring additional information from providers and/or manual review of data included in Profiles.
 - Adding fields to enable automated ordering, management of access and use for resources.
- Exposing catalogue operators and their catalogues in the EOSC Marketplace to allow direct access.
- Enhancing the Data Source subprofile schema with additional information
 - categories such as data or metadata provisioning, aggregator or repository,

¹¹ Total profiles in the Catalogue may differ from the total in the Marketplace if there are any non-active records, e.g. some services are suspended because of pending issues identified during audits by EPOT.

- jurisdiction,
- thematic area or domain,
- research entity types,
- harvesting/access protocols.
- Enabling direct links to datasets that may not be contained in any sort of Data Source.
- Creating subprofiles of services to model
 - computational services and infrastructure
 - data storage services and infrastructure
 - entire community catalogues.
- Extending the catalogue operator profile to more completely represent communities and “portals”, which in turn are linked to one or more specific community catalogues¹².
- Better alignment of EOSC Profile standards with other standards such as:
 - Resource Description Framework (RDF)
 - Web-Services Description Language (WSDL)
 - Compound standards developed by initiatives such as Gaia-X for services^{13,14}
 - Catalogue standards (e.g. DCAT, DCAT-AP, GeoDCAT, OGC standards)
 - Discipline specific standards such as those developed by the Global Alliance for Genomes and Health (GA₄GH)
 - Access and Use Policies (ODRL).

Some of these evolutionary aspects are illustrated in Figure 12-1 below:

Figure 12-1: Possible Future Profile Entities and Relationships

¹² As explored in

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1RXUnq6au2jJFqmQHMyRt2em5oTGTpTY_b622CaU7SWI/edit?usp=sharing

¹³ <https://gaia-x.eu/news/latest-news/the-role-of-ontologies-in-gaia-x/>

¹⁴ <https://service.tib.eu/webvowl/#iri=https://pastebin.com/raw/Dd7QtF38>